

PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF MILITARY PATRIOTIC EDUCATION IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: this article provides information about the concept of patriotic education and the national, historical basis for educating primary school students in the spirit of patriotism, the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism.

Keywords: president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ancestors, patriotic education, education, upbringing, concept of educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotic education, lesson, pupils, National-Spiritual Values, methods, folk pedagogy.

Patriotic education is understood in the spirit of trust and loyalty to the power of Uzbekistan, to a prosperous future, to contribute to what is being done along the way, to know what is happening in it, to know its historical, national, cultural and spiritual values, to deeply study and honor concepts related to state significance, to be personally responsible as an armed defender in Patriotism is the realization of high faith, responsibility to the motherland and the nation, high duty. The hadith, which is passed down from the ancestors to the descendants, says, "love the homeland is from faith." If we look at our long history, we will witness that the sense of faith in the motherland has long been revered by our people. We can learn through the actions of famous people who have matured from among our ancestors, their hard work on the path of the prosperity of the Fatherland, their works that have come down to us, as well as through folk oral creativity.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan SH.M.Mirziyoyev noted, " the new society we are building relies on high spiritual and moral values and places great emphasis on their development. This process is based on the idea and ideology of national independence, the upbringing of the growing young generation in the spirit of patriotism."

The work of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism is regularly organized on a systematic and scientific basis.

The system of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism consists of:

Preschool education, general secondary education, vocational education and higher education institutions aimed at the formation and development of values of socio-spiritual significance in the educational process, the spirit of love and loyalty to the motherland;

State and non-profit organizations that carry out mass and military-patriotic work, as well as other organizations.

The following are the basic principles of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism:

- science;
- historicism;
- accuracy and agility;
- regularity;

activism;

harmony of educational and educational work; consistency of the upbringing process; reliance on positive results and achievements achieved in military-patriotic education.

The methods of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism are aimed at the formation in young people of the necessary vital knowledge, skills, skills and strong will, high spiritual and moral qualities, consisting of factors that affect their consciousness, psyche and activity.

The following are ways to educate young people in the spirit of military patriotism:

persuasion;

exercise and independent work;

observation; promotion;

example and personal example.

The education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism is organized in various forms, including scientific and practical conferences, question and answer nights, reading, Games, meetings with famous people and other forms. They provide a variety of spiritual and educational work, ultimately serving to form a healthy socio-spiritual environment in society.

The following forms will be of priority in this:

lecture, Q & A nights, solo and collective conversations;

meetings with military personnel and veterans with rich life experience, individuals who have won various competitions and competitions in the fields of science, culture and sports;

scientific-theoretical and practical conferences, seminars and trainings, evenings on a specific topic, discussions, quizzes, round tables;

study and popularization of accumulated advanced experiences;

public opinion and the study of the spiritual and spiritual environment in military communities;

the use of TV shows and radio shows, movies and cartoons, artistic and musical works, Soldier Songs, media, websites and electronic games and other technical means;

Educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism

Concept – developed on the basis of the basic principles and priorities of the state youth policy implemented in the country, in the current complex era of globalization, current tasks related to the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism in a rapidly developing environment of information and communication technologies and ways to solve them, determine the role and importance of state and non-governmental organizations, This is reported by the press service of the Ministry of Defense.

The work of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism is carried out mainly in four stages:

The first stage (3-7 years old) is the stage in which children are taught various poems, songs and songs in family and preschool institutions, showing cartoons and various games, realizing the world through painting, in which the initial visions of the surrounding world, the homeland, which involve the formation of love for the motherland, appear based on acquaintance with state symbols (flag, coat of arms, anthem).

At the second stage (children aged 7-16 years), students are encouraged to do noble things, such as strengthening love and loyalty to the motherland, increasing their passion for military service and fulfilling the duty of procreation before the motherland with high

responsibility, further strengthening positive thoughts about our Armed Forces, forming youth as physically healthy, strong and strong spiritual,

The third stage (adolescents aged 16-18) is aimed at ensuring the spiritual and physical training of young people worthy of serving and protecting the motherland.

The fourth stage (18-30 years old) ensures the physical and spiritual ability of young people, leadership skills and intellectual potential, general and professional competence, regular work on oneself, encouraging them to live a healthy life and achieving it.

This concept serves as a methodological basis for improving the effectiveness of military-patriotic education among young people, increasing the high spiritual and moral qualities in them, civic position, love for the motherland and knowledge and skills aimed at preserving it as a tear.

The implementation of the concept makes it possible to raise a sense of patriotism in the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, increase the responsibility to serve the motherland faithfully and faithfully, fill the ranks of our national army with modern knowledge and professional qualifications, strong will, young people with an active civic position.

The fact that students and young people have theoretical and practical knowledge of military patriotic education, prepare them for military service on all sides and fulfill their duty to protect the prosperity of independent Uzbekistan is one of the important tasks of pedagogical communities of educational institutions.

The science of "military patriotic education" will help to successfully solve it. Organizes the organization, content, forms and methods of training students in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan spiritually – politically, psychologically and physically.

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